

THE ROLE OF TOTAL QUALITY IN HIGHER PROFESSIONAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract

“Education is an admirable thing, but it is well to remember from time to time that nothing that is worth knowing can be taught.”

- Oscar Wilde

Values and ethics are the roots of sustainability. The hub of this existence is the development of knowledge that leads to a higher quality of mind and human being. This paper discusses the role of professional institutions, involved in departing higher education to the coming generation of India, in injecting values and ethics among the masses either the faculty or student. Additionally the existing teaching methodology of higher education has been considered, its effectiveness has been evaluated and the required transformations have been suggested.

The paper focuses on the role of professional institutions that are involved in departing higher education among the masses and at the same track injecting values among the students. The paper draws a conclusion about the cause and effect relationship of imparting values in professional education. It suggests the institutions about the future benefits that could occur while imparting values while providing higher professional education to the students.

Key words: *Professional education, injecting values, imparting values, teaching methodology*

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INTRODUCTION

“Education is simply the soul of a society as it passes from one generation to another.”--

Gilbert K. Chesterton

The rapid developments in science and technology and the challenges of globalization are posing additional challenges to the education system in the country. The adverse effects of the media on the mental development and moral values of the younger generation are being felt increasingly in all spheres of life. Exploitation of natural resources is proceeding without reference to sustainability. The hiatus between the rich and the poor is getting wider. While the education system needs to keep pace with the scientific and technological developments in terms of building the skills and knowledge, it also needs to address the more fundamental issues of the social and moral consequences of such unregulated activities. There is a growing demand to lay greater emphasis on education to inculcate, nurture and develop values, particularly among the youth of the country.

“When people speak of values they are usually referring to those beliefs held by individuals to which they attach special priority to worth, and by which they tend to

order their lives. A value is, therefore, more than a belief; but it is also more than a feeling.” -- Hill (1991:4)

Values are central to both the theory of education and its practical implication. Value based education system draws a balance between the economic growth and deliverance of professional education. The focus is drawn here on personal and social values, moral values. It is only when there is a right balance of the development of all our faculties that we can reach and attain the state of self-possession and self-mastery. We can then experience our true being and discover the secret of our perpetual being.

Objective of the study

The study is conducted to analyze the present scenario prevailing in Higher and Professional Institutions and to understand their role in imparting values among the various masses of the society. The study helps in evaluating various ways adopted by professional institutions in injecting values in the students. The various other objectives of the study are as under:

1. To help in creating passion, consciousness & obligation to values for betterment of society by way of professional and ethical education.

2. To encourage various institutions to commence intellectual activities pertaining to teaching and research in respect of values and culture
3. To encourage professional institutions to prepare the requisite teaching material relating to values.

Scope of inculcating Values in Professional Education

Values are virtues, ideals and qualities on which actions and beliefs are based. Values are guiding principles that shape our world outlook, attitudes and conduct. Values present a true perspective of the development of any society or nation. They tell us to what extent a society or nation has developed itself. As the era of modernization has spread its wings in Indian culture so the requirement of providing higher and professional education arises. At the same time the responsibility of these institutions begins to instill values among the students. The paper focuses on the major areas where the scope of this perspective emerges in various fields of the economy.

- It helps in reducing lack of respect for the sanctity of human life.
- It helps in sinking the lack of respect for authority.

- It helps in securing regard for rules and regulations.
- It helps in reducing the rate abuse of alcohol and drugs.
- It helps in reducing the abuse of women and children, and other vulnerable members of society.
- It helps in banking the respect for other people and property.

An effective and value based education system helps in securing and solving the various moral and ethical problems and also the causes of the problems. The youth educated today are tomorrow's future responsible citizens. If Value based Higher and Professional education is given today, the future of the next generations will be morally and ethically well balanced and developed.

Role of Professional Institutions

Value based education is a tool which not only provides a profession to pursue but also a purpose in life. It helps in understanding the needs and to find the prioritized goals. A modern professional institution should recognize the need of value based education by considering the following -:

1. Value based professional education has to be universally applicable to all.
2. Value based professional education has to be based on reasoning and not on blind belief.
3. Value based professional education should aim at transforming living and consciousness.
4. Value based professional education has to lead to harmony within and with others.

Any institution can work on these aspects by implementing the following procedure in the institution-:

1. To organized value oriented workshops and campaigns.
2. To arrange for student empowerment programmes.
3. To provide yoga and meditation sessions for the students.
4. To arrange guest lectures for the students so that they may learn about the working culture.
5. To provide training assistance to the students to make them learn about

how to balance between professional and societal life.

An overview of various workshops and campaigns

1. Deal Shaping Workshop

The deal shaping workshop is an interactive session where the opportunity pursuit team will apply the Value Selling approach to live opportunities under the guidance of an experienced Deal Shaper. This focuses on-:

- Value Messaging.
- Staging plan to execute decision making deliverables and eliminate vulnerability

2. Student Empowerment for informed decision-making

This session will focus on proposals for capacity building for students by developing information tools on quality higher education provision worldwide.

3. Value Based Workshop

The Participants consider how to effectively synthesize their personal values with their organization's to build a value-based culture.

Working Model of Value Based Education System

Recommendations

1. The need of the hour is to inculcate human values in the Professional Students like quest for peace, adherence to truth and right beings, respect for the Motherland and the glory of its culture and traditions in order to promote societal concern and responsible citizenship; so that such an effort is in the interest of the students, society and the nation. The Government and Private Institutions

may take up the nodal responsibility for this.

2. It is entirely feasible to inculcate “values” in the students at the Professional and Higher level of education and there are several institutions in the country where such value based professional education is imparted with impressive results. It requires sustained efforts to practice, absorb and assimilate values.

3. It is desirable that human values should permeate and form a Value Based Professional Education cell to depart value based education among the students to nurture and develop societal and moral values among them.
4. Private Universities and Institutions can work towards involving Values and ethics as a subject in the syllabus of all professional students.
5. Recognizing the special role of teachers in this effort, it would be desirable to impart them the necessary skills and insight into value education by devising suitable oriented courses and extending support to the institutions for imparting such training.
6. Due recognition should be given to the expanding socially relevant role of education and to explore the methods of communicating and internalizing values among professional students.
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